

GRANT AGREEMENT 687676 (H2020-ICT-2015/H2020-ICT-2015)

Deliverable Cover Sheet

Context:

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Deliverable name	Project Handbook and Quality Plan

Included with the deliverable Executive Summary Abstract Table of Contents

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Release approval	Date	Name & organisation	Role
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V1.1	Clarified the roles of the Project Coordinator and Project Manager.	23 March 2016
V1.2	Updated the project meetings in 4.5. Added the templates as annexes. Other minor amendments have been made throughout the document.	30 June 2016

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PROJECT HANDBOOK

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Executive Summary

The purpose of this document is to provide an overview of the internal management, administrative and quality procedures of the BEACONING project in order to ensure efficient project execution as well as high quality project results. The document will provide partners with a concise reference to the project management structure, tasks, responsibilities, reporting requirements, finance information and quality processes.

1 Introduction

1.1 Summary

This document specifically covers the following areas:

- A summary of the European Commission's requirements.
- Administrative project management processes that ensure accurate financial reporting and justification of the work being carried out.
- General project management processes that ensure tight co-ordination of activities resulting in high quality deliverables.
- An internal communication strategy that ensures clear and effective communication between the Partners and that allows for the early escalation and the timely resolution of management and technical issues.
- Details of the process for the quality review of project deliverables.
- External communication, dissemination and exploitation processes that ensure a unified presentation of the project to the public at large as well as protect the IPR of the Partners. (Further details will be provided within the BEACONING Communication and Dissemination Plan.)

1.2 Precedence

The general principles for the project execution have been defined in the EC Grant Agreement (GA), the Description of Action (DoA) and the Consortium Agreement (CA). The Project Handbook does not replace any of these established agreements, or replace any of the EC guidelines for project implementation and documentation.

All partners have received a copy of the Grant Agreement from the Project Coordinator for information and guidance for project activities. A copy of the Grant Agreement and its Annexes are available online within the project's repository.

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2 Project Outline

BEACONING stands for 'Breaking Educational Barriers with Contextualised, Pervasive and Gameful Learning'. The project aims to exploit and integrate pervasive, context-aware and gamified techniques and technologies, framed within the Problem-Based Learning context towards facilitating 'anytime anywhere' learning.

2.1 Project Description

BEACONING sets a forefront in multifaceted education technologies through large-scale piloting of a digital learning platform that blends physical and digital spaces. As innovation action strategies, pilots combine opportunities for new ICTs in multiple ways that merge learning acquired in formal, non-formal and informal means, developing the skills for today's abled and disabled learners and workforce. The BEACONING platform will be a ubiquitous solution that exploits advances in user experience design, mobile communication, location-based and context aware systems, procedural content generation, pedagogy-driven gamification, learning analytics and cloud technology through innovative integration towards a blended learning space.

The BEACONING demonstrator will facilitate, assess and author gamified learning activities, integrating existing educational tools and services of the participating organisations. Focusing on STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics), the cross-subject approach embedded in a Problem-Based Learning model will contextualise learning within real world problem solving and applications. The role of learners is amplified in the process of filtering and connecting concepts framed under practical, investigative and exploratory scenarios. Large-scale pilots will validate and inform the development of the BEACONING ecosystem that democratises learning across and among fully abled and those with mild to moderate physical and mental impairments (age 15 to 24), undergoing general and vocational training.

BEACONING anticipates the benefits of making cross-subject matter more understandable, fostering the application of subject specialism to other domains. The pilot substantiates the technical and economic viability and the impact of the innovative platform to strategize market adoption and replication. By integrating experiences in a highly engaging, contextualized and personalised manner, learning can go beyond the barriers of space and time.

The Beaconing Project is composed of 7 work packages, structured according to the following image.

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2.2 Work Package 1 - Project Management

This task will be under the responsibility of the Project Coordinator and include all the reporting aspects as defined in the Quality Plan and required by the H2020 Framework Program Rules. Official Progress and Financial Reports will be produced at the end of M18 and at the end of the project (M36) containing a management-level overview of the activities carried out, a description of progress toward the scientific and technological objectives, a description of progress toward the milestones and deliverables, and identification of problems encountered during the project and the action taken to correct them.

The project management team will ensure timely production of progress reports issued for each project period, as required by EU contracts. This will be done not only to keep the commission services up-to-date regarding the status but will primarily be carried out as a means to communicate with project participants in order to monitor activity progress and resource consumption. It will be the basis for internal project monitoring and control.

2.3 Work Package 2 - Dissemination and Communication

The main objective of this WP is to increase the visibility of the project and to ensure that the outcomes of the project have a significant impact across Europe. In the medium and long term, the aim of this WP is to create and nurture the core of an ecosystem that will guarantee sustainability and adoption of project results in real contexts. The target audience will be as broad as possible, with a focus on both academia and industry.

Through the activities in this WP we aim to communicate and potentiate BEACONING's impact, seeking a return on investment for both research partners and SMEs supporting a concrete commercial exploitation strategy. The idea behind exploitation activities is also to reinforce the serious games market in general and to make the activity of designing and selling serious games more advantageous for all involved stakeholders.

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Finally, this WP also aims to disseminate across Europe the impact that these achievements can have for European citizens, with special attention to how this affects the employability of our future workforce. This WP will also include technology watch to ensure exploitation and impact is optimised. Activities include:

- Development of an active dissemination strategy for spreading project outcomes to the target stakeholders.
- Spreading knowledge and awareness around the potential of pervasive games, in order to build a solid understanding of the approaches and the solutions that are advanced within the project and increase the interested stakeholders and active actors in the market.

2.4 Work Package 3 - Requirements, Design and Specification

This WP scopes the architectural specifications taking into account disability standards based on the analysis of the stakeholders and their requirements. Scoping will inform about where and how many accessible elements or features are required under present disability accessibility standards. A technical provisions exercise follows to establish the components, dimensionality of implementation and design details of the accessible elements. Both low and high level architecture will be defined in this WP to ensure the granularity of the different modules and the components that will make up the BEACONING infrastructure and its platform.

This WP also covers the design of a framework for the Problem-Based Learning as a means of mapping active learning activities and interventions to meaningful play and game mechanics capitalising on the Serious Games Mechanics mapping of HWU and COVUNI. Additionally, this WP specifies the technical architecture of the platform and its modules, as well as of the ecosystem. The WP will provide input to WP4 to aid the integration design and framework for the complete prototype. Furthermore, the requirements will be verified or revised in the small scale testing in order to ensure that we meet specifically the requirements of user groups with special needs. Consequently, the specification and the architecture will be updated before large scale testing takes place. The approach reflects the holistic and modular approach from learning specification (layer 1 and 2) through to games (layer 3) and technological (layer 4) specifications.

2.5 Work Package 4 - Platform Development and Ecosystem Integration

WP4 is primarily to realise BEACONING Platform components (software and hardware) into an ecosystem of pervasive learning experiences driven by gamified and game-based lesson plans. The specific objectives: (a) development of the core BEACONING Platform supporting services and communication framework with a focus on interoperability and governing industrial practices; (b) implementation of context-awareness providers that will supply location and sensory information; (c) development of a multi-platform game and graphics engine coupled with a reuse-driven assets library which will be employed for digital game integration; (d) development of a modular play-learn authoring tool with procedural content generation; (e) elaboration of procedural content generation guidelines to assist content reuse in pervasive learning ecosystems; (f) development of a gamified user interface with social elements; (g) integration of a learning semantics and learning analytics system; and (h) development of gamified and game-based lesson plans and assessment metrics.

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The project adopts an agile industrial-strengthened approach to ensure timely development of a robust and high level performance platform. Based on an agile methodology, the development processes follow an iterative lifecycle (WP3-WP4-WP5) where developments are validated and evaluated in small-scale setup within WP3 (specification) and pre-pilot in real-life scenarios within WP5 (testing)

2.6 Work Package 5 - Unit Testing and Small Scale Pilot

This task is part of the iterative process where the platform prototype will be single and integrated tested, to be evaluated in a small-scale test bed. The project will include some of the learners at the identified test beds for the large scale pilot in WP6. This will include an estimated 60 learners at ORT training centres (France) and around 10-20 learners from each of the other test beds (UK, RO, TUR, IT) as recruited and engaged in WP3.

The main objectives are to:

- Test the single components
- Test the integrated platform
- Execute the small scale pilots
- Introduce recommendations for large scale testing based on small scale pilot results

The outcomes of this WP will inform the iterative WP3-WP4 process and provide insights for large-scale pilot stage in WP6.

2.7 Work Package 6 - Large Scale Pilot

The large-scale pilots aim at validating BEACONING integrated solutions scalability in real-life educational contexts by addressing large user groups. In contrast to WP5's small scale pilots, the large scale pilots will be designed top-down starting with the engagement of networks of schools through to educational NGO's. The target audience will be of significant size and involving large and heterogeneous groups of learners. Specific studies, also leveraging online surveys, will be deployed for performing network analysis with the objective of establishing the large scale pilot target participant groups addressing cross-cutting school topics as well as intra- / inter school relations. The pilots will primarily focus on engineering, entrepreneurship and that of developing of STEM and digital skills. The exact content will be defined in WP3 and developed in WP4. This top-down approach will ensure knowledge transfer from one community to another as well as additional actors in the value chain. Large scale pilots will be deployed in 5 different countries: France, Israel (ORT), Greece (ORT-UTH), Turkey (SEBIT) and Romania (SIVCO - ATS) involving a total of 5000 users.

This WP will be implemented using outcomes from WPs 3, 4 (needs, user models, and specs) and WP5 (small scale pilots). The partners will use the gathered information and feedback in order to fine-tune the technical specifications of the educational content/tool. The large pilots will inform upon how innovation can be made upon ICT and education to create fit-for-purpose digital technologies for learning. It should give us a view on how to remove obstacles for ubiquitous learning. It should also provide insights to the likelihood of uptake as a business and its adoption in WP7.

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2.8 Work Package 7 - Exploitation, Impact and Standards

The main objective of this WP is to increase large-scale visibility and persistent impacts of project results at European and international level during the whole duration of the project and beyond. In the medium and long term, the aim of this WP is to create and nurture the core of an ecosystem that will guarantee sustainability and adoption of project results in real contexts and in the broadest possible community in order to allow research partners and SMEs a return on investment and a concrete commercial exploitation possibility. The idea behind exploitation activities is also to reinforce the digital games market in general and to make the activity of designing and selling digital games, especially serious games, more advantageous for all involved stakeholders. This WP will also include technology watch to ensure exploitation and impact is optimised. Exploitation in BEACONING focuses along the three axes:

- Development of an exploitation strategy including business models that will allow sustainable project results beyond the project lifetime and enable adopters to implement these.
- Exploit the learning experiences of BEACONING via companies, organizations, and interested parties.
- Foster collaboration with the stakeholders of education programs.
- BEACONING at the fingertip: contribute to standards; exploit connectivity to existing e-Learning environments, to social sites, to relevant meeting points in the (social) Web.

3 Project Organisational Structure

3.1 Overview

The organisational structure of the Consortium shall comprise the following Consortium Bodies:

General Assembly as the ultimate decision-making body of the consortium.

Executive Board as the supervisory body for the execution of the Project which shall report to and be accountable to the General Assembly.

The Project Coordinator is the legal entity acting as the intermediary between the Parties and the Funding Authority. The Coordinator shall, in addition to its responsibilities as a Party, perform the tasks assigned to it as described in the Grant Agreement and this Consortium Agreement.

The project's management and administrative functions will be provided as shown below:

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3.2 General Assembly (GA)

The General Assembly (GA) will be chaired by the Project Coordinator (PC) and will be formed by representatives from each partner. Each partner will nominate an individual as its representative either before or at the kick-off meeting. The partner representative will have the authority to commit the partner to decisions, and will be responsible for submitting any technical document contributions required to the appropriate WP Leader, and supervise the preparation of any technical deliverable for which the partner is responsible.

Where the nominated representative is unavailable, a substitute can attend and vote at project meetings. In this instance or where there is a change to a nominated representative, the partner should notify the Project Manager (PM) at the first opportunity.

The General Assembly is responsible for the:

- determination of the overall project strategy
- overall co-ordination of project developments
- oversight of partners’ utilisation of the resources allocated to the project
- achievement of the set objectives
- authorisation of amendments to the contract
- monitoring of project progresses, achievements, and costs
- overseeing of the dissemination and exploitation of project results and outputs.

3.3 Executive Board (EB)

The Executive Board is the supervisory body for the execution of the project which reports to and is accountable to the GA. The EB is responsible for ensuring that GA decisions are implemented, as well as ensuring project compliance with the Grant Agreement/ Description of Action. The EB is made up of the WP Leaders and one other voted for by the Consortium if deemed necessary.

3.4 Project Coordinator (PC)

The Project Coordinator (PC) (Sylvester Arnab), together with the Project Manager (PM) (Jayne Beaufoy) will be responsible for the overall project (quality and financial)

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management. With the support of the project team, the PC will directly work with the WP Leaders who will keep the Team informed about the evolution of the activities carried out and send alerts when any potential issue may happen. The PC and PM are also responsible for the Management WP1 and have to ensure that all project documents are prepared with the contribution of all partners. In the execution of its functions, the PC will perform his/her actions with the other members of the Project Board.

The Project Coordinator and Project Manager will be the sole link between the consortium and the EC Project Officer. The European Commission Project Officer is directly responsible for overseeing progress and reviewing the project. Any questions that partners may have should be passed to the Project Team to either resolve or escalate to the EC Project Officer.

3.5 Technical Coordinator (TC)

The Technical Coordinator (TC) (Ioana Stefan) supports the PC and is responsible for coordinating the tasks. The TC supervises the activities in the work packages and ensures compliance with the project plan. The TC will also take responsibility for dissemination and policy communication relating to work packages and sustaining the results of the project.

The TC provides a robust managerial structure to ensure the delivery of efficient and effective project activity and far-reaching project results.

The TC will liaise directly with the partners and ensure a seamless communication process with the PC and PM on matters of project progress and technical issues. The TC, PC and PM will communicate regularly to discuss issues, align strategies and coordinate activities and hold online meeting.

3.6 Work Package Leaders (WPLs)

WP No.	Description	WP Leader	Leader Name
WP1	Project Management	1 COVUNI	Sylvester Arnab
WP2	Dissemination and Communication	5 UCM	Baltasar Fernandez Manjon
WP3	Requirements, Design and Specification	3 BIBA	Jannicke Baalsrud Hauge
WP4	Platform Development and Ecosystem Integration	8 ATS	Ioana Stefan
WP5	Unit Testing and Small Scale Pilot	6 ORT	Raphael Attias
WP6	Large Scale Pilot	6 ORT	Raphael Attias
WP7	Exploitation, Impact and Standards	13 SEBIT	Ali Turker

Work Package Leaders (WPLs) will be directly managed by the TC, the TC will then regularly update the PM. The WPLs have detailed co-ordination of their WP, which entails the definition of the roles of the partners as well as the preparation, planning, undertaking and reporting of the activities of the WP. The WP Leader(s) will, therefore, be responsible for achieving the objectives, for the quality of the products and for technical reporting to the PC and the General Assembly any conflicts or problems that can arise within their WP. The WPLs must have a global vision of the activities of the various WPs. In particular, the WP leaders will have to carry out the following tasks:

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- coordinate the work of the other organisations involved within the WP;
- organise meetings with the other partners involved in the WP, when this is necessary, in order to ensure that the envisaged activities are carried out, the objectives and products are obtained and deadlines are respected. (Wherever possible, WP meetings should take place alongside plenary meetings);
- contribute to ensuring the coordination and communication of all the horizontal activities;
- report to the General Assembly any conflicts or problems that can arise within their WP;
- maintain close contact with the PC and Project Team;
- fully participate within the overall monitoring activities carried out by the PM, including submitting a regular report of activities within the work package;
- work closely to support the activities of Task Leaders;
- provide inputs for the preparation of the project newsletters;
- co-operate in the implementation of all the dissemination activities;
- attend/present on activity relating to the WP at Commission Technical Review Meetings.

3.7 Task Leaders (TL)

Task Leaders will be directly managed by their appropriate WP Leader(s) and will be in charge of:

- ensuring the correct procedures during their task lifecycle in order to get the best results;
- informing their WP Leader about any technical, procedural, administrative issue that could prevent the task and activity from getting the best results;
- working closely with the other partners involved within their tasks;
- participate within Commission Technical Review Meetings, as appropriate.

3.8 External Advisory Board (EAB)

The External Advisory Board (EAB) is composed of prominent members of the European community. The purpose of the Board is to provide technical expertise and advice to the project across a range of disciplines related to the project's work.

The EAB will conduct most of its business electronically; where necessary it will meet once a year at a time concurrent with other project meetings. Members will also be invited to major project events such as the international conferences.

4 Communications

4.1 General Assembly Meeting Rules

The following section summarises the rules and procedures for GA Meetings.

The details provided here are aligned to the project's Consortium Agreement; the document that is agreed by the General Assembly. Should there be any discrepancy between this handbook and the Consortium Agreement, the conditions of the Consortium Agreement will take precedence.

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4.1.1 Purpose

The GA Meetings serve as a forum for making decisions concerning the progress and outcome of the project.

4.1.2 General Rules

These will be in line with the standards agreed within the Consortium Agreement.

Meeting Notice: The Coordinator must give notice in writing 45 calendar days prior to holding a face-to-face meeting or 7 calendar days prior to holding a teleconference.

Special Meetings: The Project Coordinator shall convene extraordinary meetings at any time upon written request of 1/3 of members of the GA.

Agenda Notice: The Project Coordinator must send the agenda 14 calendar days prior to a face-to-face meeting or 3 working days prior to a teleconference.

Agenda Contributions: Any Partner may submit agenda items up until 7 calendar days prior to a face-to-face meeting, 1 day before a teleconference or online meeting or on the day of meeting with unanimous approval of the GA.

Any agenda item requiring a decision by members of the GA must be identified as such on the agenda.

Minutes: The Project Team must make the minutes available within 10 calendar days of the meeting. Partners may comment on the minutes up until 15 calendar days after the minutes have been made available. Following this, the minutes are considered accepted and published online in the reserved area of the project's website.

4.1.3 Voting

Quorum: Two-thirds of the GA members must be present to establish a Quorum for formal deliberations to take place.

Voting Representative: Each Partner has one vote, if absent then the Project Coordinator as the lead will have the partner vote and decisions will be taken on a majority basis.

Proxy: Each Partner may appoint a substitute or a proxy to attend and vote at any meeting; however, this must be submitted in writing to the Project Manager prior to the meeting.

Decision Making: The GA shall attempt to make decisions by consensus by the unanimous vote of all members present or represented, but where this is not possible, a simple majority vote is required for most decisions (as detailed within the Consortium Agreement).

IPR-related Decisions: These decisions require a unanimous vote.

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Defaulting Parties / Project Termination or Suspension: These decisions require a unanimous vote.

4.1.4 Veto

Right to Veto: A Partner has the right to veto, if it can show that its own work, time for performance, costs, liabilities, intellectual property rights or other legitimate interests would be severely affected by a specific decision.

Veto Vote: In the case of a veto, each Partner must be present to vote if the decision has been included on the agenda prior to the meeting.

4.2 General Assembly Meeting Role

General Assembly meetings will be organised to evaluate overall progress and achievement, co-ordinate project-related interactions among partners and evaluate progress against project plans, identifying and contemplating any major problems and deviations from the project time-schedule.

4.3 Conflict Resolution

Conflict Resolution Procedures: Special focus will be kept on areas that most likely might lead to conflicting situations. The PM and TC will directly deal with the WP leaders who will keep the PC informed about the evolution of the activities carried out and send alerts when any potential issue may happen. The PC will have then to assess and mitigate any conflict amicably. If the issue cannot be solved, then the PC will submit it to the GA for discussion and if necessary a vote to resolve the issue.

4.4 Emergency Procedure / Conflict Resolution

In the event that an issue should arise that could jeopardize the overall completion date of the project or the quality of the delivered results it should be reported immediately to the PC and PM. The Project Coordinator will endeavour to resolve the issue as soon as possible by calling an emergency Project Board Meeting and/or General Assembly Meeting, depending upon the issue, in order to determine the next steps.

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4.5 Project Meetings

The following meetings are scheduled within the BEACONING project.

Year	Host	Type	Tentative period	Days
1	COVUNI (Coventry, UK)	GA MEETING Kick off meeting	19-20 January 2016	1.5
	INESC (Porto, Portugal)	GA MEETING Plenary 1 + Specification workshop (<i>lead BIBA</i>)	14-16 June 2016	2.5
2	UCM (Madrid, Spain)	GA MEETING Plenary 2 + Integration design workshop (<i>lead ATS</i>)	January/February 2017	2.5
	ATS (Bucharest, Romania)	GA MEETING Plenary 3 + Technical integration workshop (<i>lead ATS</i>)	May/June 2017	2.5
	Commission Luxembourg/ Demo Site	EXECUTIVE MANAGEMENT BOARD Review meeting (only coordinator and WP leads) - for reporting period M1-M18	June/July 2017	2
3	ORT (Paris, France)	GA MEETING Plenary 4 + Pilot and Trials workshop (<i>Lead ORT</i>)	January/February 2018	2.5
	SEBIT (Istanbul, Turkey)	GA MEETING Plenary 5 + Exploitation workshop (<i>Lead SEBIT</i>)	June/July 2018	2.5
	Commission Luxembourg	GA MEETING Final Review meeting (all partners) – for reporting period M19-M36	December 2018/January 2019	2
	Total			18

Each partner will pay travel and subsistence costs through their part of the project budget.

Where there is a need for a project meeting, to save costs, it is best to schedule it at the same time as a project event.

General Assembly meetings are physical meetings attended by a representative of each of the project partners or online if required. Ideally, they should take place at six monthly intervals and/or be tied in with project conferences or events.

Workshops will also be held throughout the duration of the project, these should be attended by a representative of the project partners, especially if they are involved in the WP.

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The External Advisory Board is formed to advise the project on its course of action. Meetings can be arranged either online or during project conferences/events, with ongoing discussions taking place through e-mail. Content of meetings is defined by the Project Coordinator, Project Manager and/or Technical Coordinator.

Meetings for the Project Board and all Work Package leaders can be called as required and are likely to take place online.

Intra-Work Package/Task Meetings will be called when specific needs arise, even at a short notice, in order to discuss and solve technical problems or related to specific tasks such as undertaking work towards the development and writing of a project deliverable. As with GA meetings, wherever possible, these should be tied in with other project events.

Regular work package conference calls, monthly project conference calls will take place as well as communication by e-mail and telephone and arranged between partners.

Copies of meeting minutes, with details of all decisions taken at any meeting should be forwarded to the Project Manager. These minutes will be the responsibility of the Work Package or Task Leader, responsible for calling the meeting, and as in section 4.1.2 above, they should be produced within 10 calendar days of the meeting having taken place.

Technical Review Meetings will provide, together with Deliverables and Reports, the means to allow the Commission to check and validate Project progress. Technical review meetings are called by the Commission. The agenda of the meeting is agreed between the Commission and the PC: the agenda of the project's presentation within the general agenda is agreed amongst the partners and provided by the PC to the Commission.

Where partners wish to suggest a change to the DoA, they should do so by using the Amendment to DoA form, available on the partners website repository; a copy is provided in section 8.

4.6 Mailing Lists and Address Book

A series of project mailing lists have been created which will ensure that all partners are included in relevant e-mail conversations. A composition list of each mailing list will be saved within the project document repository SharePoint.

The following project mailing lists will be available to facilitate making requests to the appropriate partner representatives:

- Consortium members – consortium@beaconing.eu
- Executive Board – eb@beaconing.eu
- Individual Work Packages – wp1@beaconing.eu (wp2, wp3, wp4, wp5, wp6, wp7)
- External Advisory Board – ab@beaconing.eu
- Financial contacts – financial@beaconing.eu

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The definition of these lists may vary dependent upon the requirements of partners.

Partners should contact the Project Manager when a person is to be added or removed from the list.

4.7 Document Sharing

Partners will have access to a secure restricted area within the Beaconing website. Official project documents should be shared between partners using the filing system set up in line with project Work Packages.

For day-to-day operation, partners should share working documents using a SharePoint site managed by Coventry University. These arrangements will be agreed at Work Package and/or Task levels for particular project activity.

Where it is required to share a physical project document, partners:

- are advised to use a courier service to mail any legal or signed documents.
- should keep a copy of all signed documents for their own records.

4.8 Project Event Schedule

The following events are scheduled within the BEACONING project.

Workshops and Conferences	Target Audiences	Location	Timing/Date
UK regional (final) workshop	UK stakeholders	COVUNI	1 day
Spanish regional (final) workshop	Spanish stakeholders	UCM	1 day
Romanian regional (final) workshop	Romanian stakeholders	SIVECO	2 days
French regional (final) workshop	French stakeholders	ORT	2 days
German regional (final) workshop	German stakeholders	BIBA	1 days
Turkey regional (final) workshop	Turkish stakeholders	SEBIT	2 days

Each partner will pay travel and subsistence costs through their part of the project budget.

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Where there is a need for a project meeting, to save costs, it is best to schedule it at the same time as a project event.

5. Reporting

5.1 Reporting procedures, frequency and format

During the course of the project the following items need to be delivered:

- The deliverables identified in the Description of Action.
- The milestones identified in the Description of Action.
- Two Progress Reports; within 60 days of the end of each reporting period.
- A Final Report; within 60 days after the end of the project.

5.2 Report Schedule

The Project is divided into two formal reporting periods of the following duration:

Reporting Period 1 – 1st January 2016 – 30th June 2017

Reporting Period 2 – 1st July 2017 – 31st December 2018

Type of Report	Month Due	Completed by
EC Progress Reports	To be submitted 60 days after the report period	PC (supported by partners) and sent to the Commission
EC Final Reports	Final report due 60 days after the project end date	PC (supported by partners) and sent to the Commission
Timesheets	To be submitted every 3 months	All members of project team and sent to the PM electronically
Partner Finance / Activity Summary	To be submitted every 3 months	Each Partner and sent to the PM electronically
Work Package Report Form	To be submitted every 3 months	Each Work Package Leader (when WP is active) sent to Project Team electronically.

Templates for these reports are available for Partners and will be stored in the projects document repository site SHAREPOINT.

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5.3 Internal Financial and Activity Reporting

At three-monthly intervals technical and administrative information will be collected from the Partners, who will be required to deliver a progress report to the Project Manager including:

- summary of the major activities within each WP, problems and actions undertaken
- any current change from the planned activities and the reasons for this
- any changes to the planned activities which may be considered necessary within the coming period
- description of expenditure for the period
- any departure from the planned budget
- any future departure from the budget for the next period
- any management problem encountered
- list of the deliverables with their status: on time, delayed, delivery date/s, etc.
- list of main actual outputs as against those planned in the Description of Work
- financial statement and comparison with the planned resources
- dissemination activities carried out in the period
- dissemination and training events organised or participated in by the partner
- dissemination plan for the next period
- detailed activities planned for the next period

A named person within each partner organisation will be responsible for each deliverable.

As a further aspect of the reporting process, Partners will need to outline the time that their organisation has spent on any given activity in person months. There is no generic definition of a standard person month; they should be calculated based upon the number of hours per week that is considered standard within each Partner's own organisation.

The project Partners will provide this information to the Project Team on a regular basis, both informally through e-mail and formally using the templates provided.

5.4 Progress Report

At the end of each of the first two reporting periods, the Project Coordinator is required to submit a progress report summarising the activity of the partnership during that period within 60 days of the end of the reporting period.

The report should include a publishable summary, containing information about the progress of work, including achievement and attainment of any milestones and deliverables identified in the DoA. In addition, this report should contain information on resources employed and departures from the work schedule.

All Partners should contribute information to the development of the progress report, with WP Leaders co-ordinating the response to provide a critical analysis of project work undertaken and the results achieved.

As detailed within the Finance section, a financial summary for each Partner will also have to be submitted at the end of the reporting period.

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It is following the assessment and acceptance of these submissions that the Commission will make payment.

5.5 Final Report

As with the Progress Report, the Project Coordinator is required to submit a final report within 60 days after the end of project delivery.

The final report shall comprise a final publishable summary report covering the results, conclusions and social-economic impact of the project.

As with the Progress Report, input from partners is important to represent the project activities effectively and WP Leaders will play a key role in presenting the details of activity and results for their areas of work.

Financial information will also be reported for each partner to enable the Commission to calculate final payments.

The Commission can accept or reject deliverables and reports and suspend payments where this is deemed necessary.

A series of Partner financial and management reporting templates have been developed to provide information for project reporting.

5.6 Technical Review Meetings

The BEACONING project has two Technical Review meeting dates scheduled; one at the end of each reporting period.

The Technical Review will assess work carried out under the project, including evaluating reports and deliverables, the use of resources and the efficiency and effectiveness of management of the project and expected impact.

The Project Coordinator, Technical Coordinator, and all Work Package Leaders and any other specialist Partners are required to attend the review meeting and make presentations to the Commission or their selected panel of experts to outline the operation and achievements of work undertaken. Other experts, such as the Pilot Coordinators may be required to attend the Technical Review.

All Partners will be required to contribute towards the preparation of this meeting and a rehearsal day is to take place the day before meeting the Commission.

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6 Finance

6.1 Finance Explanation

Finance payments will be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement and as outlined in the Consortium Agreement. Each partner is responsible for the expenditure and costs incurred to action the project and work packages and must only attribute costs to the project that comply with the following:

- actually incurred by the beneficiary
- All expenditure must be incurred during the action duration
- entered as eligible costs in the estimated budget of the action
- connected to the action as described in Annex 1
- identifiable and verifiable
- compliance with applicable national laws on taxes, labour and social security
- reasonable, justified and must comply with the principles of sound financial management, in particular regarding economy and efficiency

The EU/Euratom grant cannot be used to finance activities other than those approved by the Commission.

6.2 Financial Reporting

Internal Financial reporting will take place on a three monthly basis to allow the co-ordinator to:

- monitor the financial progress of the project in line with work packages delivery
- monitor costs to date
- identification of any anomalies
- take corrective action to ensure successful delivery of the project.

6.3 Documentation and Audit Trail

The beneficiaries must **keep** appropriate **records** and supporting documentation to justify the expenditure for which they declare costs.

The beneficiaries must keep the original documents. Digital and digitalised documents are considered originals if they are authorised by the applicable national law.

For actual costs adequate records and other supporting documentation to prove the costs declared, such as contracts, subcontracts, invoices and accounting records will need to be retained.

For unit costs: adequate records and other supporting documentation to prove the number of units declared must be retained.

For direct personnel costs declared as unit costs calculated in accordance with the beneficiary's usual cost accounting practices must be retained.

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All evidence must be verifiable, auditable and available. The beneficiaries must — for a period five years after the payment of the balance — keep records and other supporting documentation in order to prove the proper implementation of the action and the costs they declare as eligible.

An audit trail must be traceable and available for expenditure incurred. Original supporting documentation must be retained and costs to the project must be authorised, recorded in the accounting system of the beneficiary and identifiable as project related. Costs must not be recorded twice (the same costs must not be charged against this project and another project).

The sufficiency and the persuasiveness of the evidence provided, as well as the audit trail, will be assessed against the International Standards on Auditing.

Beneficiaries who reach the €325,000 threshold must submit a certificate on the financial statement (CFS). Such a certificate is needed if the beneficiary requests a total financial contribution of EUR 325,000 (or more) as reimbursement for actual costs and personnel costs declared on the basis of unit costs calculated according to its usual accounting practices (i.e. 'average personnel costs').

This means that costs based on lump sums, flat-rates (e.g. indirect costs) or unit costs (other than those for personnel costs calculated according to the beneficiary's usual cost accounting practices costs') are not counted for the EUR 325,000 threshold (and do not need to be covered by the certificate).

7 Quality Control Procedure

7.1 Quality Assurance Peer Review

All deliverables and contractual reports generated over the duration of the project will be subject to a standard quality control procedure.

The Partner responsible for the deliverable will complete a draft version, adding the Deliverable Cover Sheet and any executive summary or abstract, as agreed with the Technical Coordinator. Two peer reviewers will be nominated for each deliverable and each reviewer will be asked to complete the Deliverable Internal Review Form, making comments to pass back to the originating Partner.

The Quality Assurance cycle will be as follows:

- The Partner responsible for the deliverable sends it to the project team, copying it to the Work Package Leader and Technical Coordinator, one month before the due delivery date.
- The Project Manager forwards the deliverable to the Partners responsible for quality peer review.
- After the review is carried out, a reviewed copy of the deliverable is returned to the author, with copy to the Project Manager, Technical Coordinator and Work Package Leader, within two weeks of receipt.
- The author will consider the comments, together with the Work Package Leader and amend the deliverable in response to the review, within a week of receiving both sets of feedback.

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- The Project Manager will carry out a final ‘superficial’ review, to ensure all templates, etc. are complied with and any minor adjustments are carried out by Project Team.
- The Project Manager forwards the deliverable to the European Commission Project Officer by the deliverable due date.
- The submitted version of the deliverable is uploaded onto the website, following acknowledgement of receipt from the Commission’s Project Officer and retained until end of project.

The following should be noted:

- The content of the deliverables is the most important material to review. Internal reviewers will be experienced in the general topic of the deliverable and be able to assess its quality. They will also be familiar with the overall project, and therefore able to judge the contribution that the deliverable makes to the project.
- The Technical Coordinator will carry out occasional spot-checks, to ensure that QA procedures are being adhered to. The importance of the review of a third party deliverable for the overall value of the project cannot be overestimated.
- The Project Manager will monitor the progress of the QA cycle. In order to allow time for review and for enhancements, the preceding stages must be completed on time. The Technical Coordinator will be made aware of the risk of late deliverables and late reviews.

It is recognised that this timetable can be subject to change during peak times and absences i.e. holidays.

Where a partner becomes aware that they will be unavailable during the dates allocated for delivery or review, or believe that they do not have the necessary competence to undertake the process, they should inform the Work Package Leader and/or the Project Manager, as soon as possible to allow appropriate action to take place.

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7.2 Project Deliverables, peer review allocation and timetable

Ref:	Title	Owner	Reviewer 1	Reviewer 2	QM	Delivery Date
MS4	Project Website Start-Up	ATS				Mar-16
D1.1	Project Handbook & Quality Plan	COVUNI	TL	AC	JBH	Jun-16
D1.2	Interim Progress & Financial Report	COVUNI	IS	AT	JBH	Jun-16
D1.7	Data Management & Ethics Process Plan	BIBA	AC	TL	IS	Jun-16
MS2	Data Management Plan	BIBA				Jun-16
D2.1	Dissemination & Communication Plan	UCM	TL	IS	JBH	Jun-16
D2.2	Project Branding & Website	ATS	SA	BF	JBH	Jun-16
MS5	Final Version of the Dissemination & Communication Plan (DCP)	UCM				Jun-16
MS6	Visual Identify Guide (VGI)	ATS				Jun-16
D3.1	Requirement Analysis	BIBA	TL	PY	IS	Jun-16
MS1	Circulating Project Handbook & Quality Plan	COVUNI				Jul-16
MS7	Definition of Learning Needs	BIBA				Jul-16
D3.2	Technology & Learning Environment Inventory	BIBA	KC	BF	JBH	Aug-16
D3.3	Learning Environment System Specification	COVUNI	BF	LM	JBH	Aug-16
MS8	Inventory of Gamified Approaches	SUCCUBUS				Aug-16
MS10	Deliver BEACONING Specification	ATS				Oct-16
D1.8	Data Management & Ethics Process Plan update 1	BIBA	AC	TL	IS	Dec-16
D3.4	Interface Design Specification	PLAYSOFT	AS	HP	JBH	Dec-16
D3.5	Game Design Document	SUCCUBUS	BF	AT	JBH	Dec-16
D4.6	Game Analytics & Adaptation Component Design	UCM	AT	TK	JBH	Dec-16
D7.1	Technology Watch	SEBIT	FM		JBH	Dec-16
D6.1	Evaluation Guidelines	SIVECO	OH	LH	JBH	Feb-17
D3.6	System Architecture	ATS	LH	LA	JBH	Mar-17
D1.3	Progress Report	COVUNI	IS	FM	JBH	Jun-17

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D1.4	Financial Report	COVUNI	CG	IS	JBH	Jun-17
D2.3	Dissemination Results 1	UCM	IS	TL	JBH	Jun-17
MS9	Inventory of Infrastructure & Engagement Elements	BIBA				Jun-17
D4.1	Integrated BEACONING Ecosystem	ATS	BF	AT	JBH	Jun-17
D4.2	Location-Based Component	IFINITY	AC	MC	JBH	Jun-17
D4.3	Games Bundle	SUCCUBUS	LuM	AS	JBH	Jun-17
D4.8	Gamified Lesson Plans	COVUNI	SiA	MC	JBH	Jun-17
MS11	Release of Platform Proof-of-Concept Alpha	ATS				Jun-17
D5.2	Integrated BEACONING Platform Test Analysis	COVUNI	IS	LuM	JBH	Jun-17
D5.3	Deployment & Pilot Guidelines & Recommendations	ORT	AB	LM	JBH	Jun-17
D6.2	Pilot Set-Up Report	SEBIT	OH	LA	JBH	Jun-17
MS17	Evaluation Framework	SIVECO				Jun-17
D7.2	Preliminary Exploitation Strategy	ORT	IS	AJ	JBH	Jun-17
MS21	Preliminary Exploitation Strategy	SEBIT				Jun-17
D5.1	Single Components User Tests Analysis	ATS	LuM	AnB	JBH	Aug-17
MS12	Release of Integrated Platform Beta for Testing	ATS				Oct-17
D1.9	Data Management & Ethics Process Plan update 2	BIBA	AC	BF	JBH	Dec-17
D4.5	BEACONING Platform GUI	HFC	TL	MP	JBH	Dec-17
D4.7	Game Analytics & Adaptation Components Reference Implementation	UCM	AT	AS	JBH	Dec-17
D7.4	BEACONING Sustainability Report	SEBIT	SA	FM	JBH	Dec-17
D7.5	Report on Standardization: Intermediate & Final	SEBIT	IS	HP	JBH	Dec-17
D3.7	Iterations, Refinement & Updates on the Specification	BIBA	TL	BF	IS	Jan-18

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D4.4	Prototype of the Authoring & Procedural System Framework Components	INESC TEC	LuM	MC	JBH	Feb-18
MS15	All Modules Validated	ATS	AnB	TL	JBH	Mar-18
MS16	Integrated Prototype Tested & Guidelines for Large-Scale Pilot	COVUNI				Apr-18
MS18	Completion of Evaluation Framework based on Platform Readiness Analysis	SIVECO				Apr-18
MS13	Final Release of Full Prototype to be used at the start of Large-Scale Pilot	ATS				May-18
MS19	Completion of Initial Round of Learning Experiments for Evaluation	SEBIT				Jul-18
D7.3	Final Exploitation Plan	ORT	MC	IS	JBH	Aug-18
MS22	Final Version of the Exploitation Plan	SEBIT				Aug-18
MS20	Completion of 2nd Round of Learning Experiments for Evaluation Purposes	SEBIT				Nov-18
D1.5	Final Report (confidential)	COVUNI	BF	IS	JBH	Dec-18
D1.6	Final Report (public)	COVUNI	TL	IS	JBH	Dec-18
D1.10	Data Management & Ethics Process Plan final update	BIBA	LH	AC	JBH	Dec-18
MS3	Delivering Final Report	COVUNI				Dec-18
D2.4	Dissemination Results 2	UCM	IS	TL	JBH	Dec-18
MS14	Final Version of the Platform Based on Pilot for Market Replication	ATS				Dec-18
D6.3	Validation & Usability Report	COVUNI	AnB	PY	JBH	Dec-18
D6.4	Finding Analysis Report	ORT	TL	LuM	JBH	Dec-18
MS23	Sustainability Plan	ORT				Dec-18
MS24	Standardization Plan	SEBIT				Dec-18

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7.3 Project Milestones

No.	Name	Lead	Expected Delivery Date
1	Circulating Project handbook and quality plan	COVUNI	01/08/2016
2	Data Management Plan	BIBA	01/07/2016
3	Delivering final report	COVUNI	01/01/2019
4	Project website start-up	ATS	01/04/2016
5	Final version of the Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP)	UCM	01/07/2016
6	Visual Identify Guide (VGI)	ATS	01/07/2016
7	Definition of learning needs	BIBA	01/08/2016
8	Inventory of gamified approaches	SUCCUBUS	01/09/2016
9	Inventory of infrastructure and engagement elements	BIBA	01/07/2017
10	Deliver BEACONING specification	ATS	01/11/2016
11	Release of platform proof-of concept Alpha	ATS	01/07/2017
12	Release of integrated platform Beta for testing	ATS	01/11/2017
13	Final release of full prototype to be used at the start of large-scale pilot	ATS	01/06/2018
14	Final version of the platform based on pilot for market replication	ATS	01/01/2019
15	All modules validated	ATS	01/04/2018
16	Integrated prototype tested and guidelines for large-scale pilot	COVUNI	01/05/2018
17	Evaluation Framework	SIVECO	01/07/2017
18	Completion of Evaluation Framework based on platform readiness analysis	SIVECO	01/05/2018
19	Completion of Initial Round of Learning Experiments for Evaluation	SEBIT	01/08/2018
20	Completion of 2nd Round of Learning Experiments for Evaluation Purposes	SEBIT	01/12/2018
21	Preliminary Exploitation Strategy	SEBIT	01/07/2017
22	Final version of the Exploitation Plan	SEBIT	01/09/2018
23	Sustainability plan	ORT	01/01/2019
24	Standardization plan	SEBIT	01/01/2019

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8. Document Templates

Various templates have been created for the project and are shown below: These templates should be used for time sheeting, progress and management reports. This will aid the collation of material for the reports to the European Commission.

Templates available are:

- Deliverables Template
- Deliverable Internal Review Form
- Work Package Report Form
- Partner Finance/Activity Summary
- Amendment to the DoA Form
- Timesheet
- Deliverable Coversheet
- Risk Management Table

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8.1

**Grant Agreement No. 687676
 Innovation Action
 ICT-20-2015**

[No. and title of the deliverable]

Due date	[Month XX]
Actual date	[Month XY]
Deliverable author(s)	
Partner(s)	
Version	
Status	
Dissemination level	

Project Coordinator

Coventry University

Sylvester Arnab

Priory Street, Coventry CV1 5FB, UK

E-mail: s.arnab@coventry.ac.uk

Project website: <http://www.beaconing.eu>

Version control				
Version	Date	Author	Institution	Change and where applicable reason for change

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Quality control				
QA Version	Date	QA Responsible	Institution	Change and where applicable reason for change

Release approval				
Version	Date	Name	Institution	Role

Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

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3 Conclusion

 3.1.....Results

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Appendix: Definitions of terms

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Sample figure

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1. Sample table

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Executive summary is written to summarize the key questions and findings of the document. It is actually a document in miniature that may be read in place of the larger document.

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Introduction

This document provides reading this should prepare the reader for the rest of the document. This, plus the conclusion, can act as a summary.

Background

Why the material in the deliverable appears in the project. Any background which sets the scene for the material herein.

Role of this Deliverable in the Project

What element or aspect of the project does this deliverable represent? How does the work reported herein contribute to the overall progress of the project?

The inputs and dependencies for the work described in deliverable.

The manner in which this deliverable feeds into further work in this and other work-packages.

Approach

Description of the work carried out, the results of which appear in this deliverable. What did people actually DO, and how? Specific protocols and standards? Using work from other WPs? Influenced by other research or projects?

Feel free to use diagrams and images wherever reasonable.

Structure of the document

Brief description of the chapters which compose the document.

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TITLE 1

TITLE 2

Title 3

Normal text.

Bulleted lists:

- Row 1
- Row 2
 - Sub-row 1
 - Sub-row 2

Numbered lists:

1. Row 1
2. Row 2
 - a. Sub-row 1
 - b. Sub-row 2

Figures:

Figure 1: Sample figure

Tables:

Column 1	Column 2
Text	Text
Text	Text

Table 1. Sample table

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Conclusion

Brief summary of the document. Take-home messages. Focus on the progress demonstrated and the next steps.

Results

Results of the work described above. Numbers, diagrams, conclusions, suggestions.

Impact

How these results contribute to the progress of the project. What new work can now start. What work-packages will this work feed into.

If broader (beyond project) impact, mention this here too.

Appendix: Definitions of terms

Glossary of terms used in the document

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8.2 Deliverable Internal Review Form

Reviewer / Partner Name			
Deliverable Number			
Deliverable Title			
Version Number		Date	
Reviewer number	1 / 2 / 3	Changes Accepted	Yes / No

1. Relevance and originality of the deliverable [1 (very low) – 6 (very high)]

[e.g. does the deliverable address the project objectives as specified within the Description of Action and does it go beyond the level of previous research undertaken?]

Does the deliverable cross ref. to other beaconing deliverables?

Technical quality of the deliverable

Presentation quality of the deliverable

[e.g. is the deliverable well written? Is it organised in a logical fashion? Is the readability good, average or poor?]

My overall recommendation is:

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Definitely accept | <input type="checkbox"/> Minor revisions required before accepting |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Major revisions required before accepting | <input type="checkbox"/> Definitely reject |

Recommend minor revisions (if any)

I have used 'track changes' to add notes directly into the deliverable

Recommend major revisions (if any)

In the case of major revisions, the revised deliverable will be reviewed again and authors will be asked to provide a short summary of revisions made.

Please provide any other comments

Follow up (Second Review cycle- only for major revisions)

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8.3 Work Package Report Form (3 Monthly)

Project acronym		Project number	
WP Number/Title			
Partner Name			
Reporting period	From		To

The description of activity provided by WP Leaders in this report will be used to inform formal reports for the Commission.

Progress Summary

Please outline the objectives for the period, together with details of progress and significant results

Task 1

Please describe the work completed during this period or write “no work planned for this period”.

Task 2

Please describe the work completed during this period or write “no work planned for this period”

Please add further Tasks, in line with your Work Package

NOTE: do not repeat content of deliverables which have been submitted, instead briefly reference them.

Deliverables schedule (Only for deliverables within your Work Package, as shown in Annex 1/DoA)

Deliverable number			
Month due (see DoW)			
Actual/forecast			

If you have forecasted a deliverable to be completed after the due date, please provide an explanation for this change.

Issues/Corrective actions/Risk

Have there been any issues that could have delayed planned activity? Do you foresee any problems that might prevent completion of future work? Describe any corrective action taken or planned.

Any Other Comments

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8.4 Partner Finance/Activity Summary

Project Acronym	BEACONING	Project Number	687676
Partner Name			
Reporting Period	From:	To:	

Please provide a summary of activity for each Work Package that your organisation has been involved with during this three-month reporting period.

Work Package 1

Work Package 2

Work Package 3

Work Package 4

Work Package 5

Work Package 6

Work Package 7

Please report upon all of the Work Packages where you have been active within the three-month reporting period. Enter the phrase “no work planned for this period” against each Work Package where there has been no activity within this three-month reporting period.

Issues/Corrective Actions/Risk

Have there been any issues that could have delayed planned activity? Do you foresee any problems that might prevent completion of future work? Describe any corrective action taken or planned.

Please provide the total number of person months used (double click to access the table)

Total Months	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	Total
--------------	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-------

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For 3 Month Period									0
Cumulative Project Total									0
Total from DoA									0
Total Months Remaining	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Please provide an explanation if your actual delivery, for each Work Package, is not expected to match the allocated number of months outlined within the DoA.

Please provide a list of publications, conferences and other BEACONING dissemination activities undertaken.

Please provide a list of relevant meetings and dates during this three months period.

Please provide a list of travel undertaken for the BEACONING project during this three-month period.

Project Expenditure

Please provide totals against each heading (double click to access the table).

Description	Actual Amount for 3 month period €	Actual Cumulative Amount for the project €	Allocation in the DoA €	Total Funding remaining €
Personnel costs				0
Travel costs				
Equipment				
Consumables				
Other direct costs				
Subcontracting				
Total Costs	0	0	0	0

Timesheets of staff involved should be submitted to the Project Manager together with this form.

Please provide an overview of your current spending profile.

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If you predict a variance from the allocation within the DoA, please provide an explanation.

Please provide any other comments.

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8.5 Request for Amendment to the DoA

Project Number		Project Acronym	
Work package		Type of activity	
Work package title			
Start month		End month	
Lead partner name		Date of request	

Description of Amendment Requested

Please insert a detailed description of the change to the DoA. This should include an explanation of the implication of leaving things how they are and why this change is in the best interests of the project.

If applicable please complete the following table with revised person-months per partner.

Person Months Per Partner			
Participant number	Participant short name	Original Person Months per participant	Revised Person Months per participant

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If applicable please complete the following table with revised deliverable information

List of Deliverables					
Deliverable Number	Deliverable Title	Lead partner	Estimated indicative person-months	Dissemination level	Delivery date

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If applicable please complete the following table with revised milestone information

List of Milestones				
Milestone number	Milestone name	Lead partner	Delivery date from Annex I	Comments

Has this request been discussed and approved by the WP partners Yes No

To be completed by the Coordinator		
Date received		
Name of reviewer		
Date reviewed		
Amendment approved	Yes	No
EB approval	Yes	No
Explanation, if request denied		

Does this request need approval by the EC Project Officer Yes No

8.6 Sample Timesheet

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8.7 Deliverable Cover Sheet

Project Acronym	
Project Number	
Project Title	

Deliverable number	
Deliverable name	

Included with the deliverable	Executive Summary	<input type="checkbox"/>	Abstract	<input type="checkbox"/>	Table of Contents	<input type="checkbox"/>
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Partner responsible for deliverable	
Deliverable author(s)	
Deliverable version number	
Target delivery date	
Actual delivery date	

Dissemination Level	
Public	<input type="checkbox"/>
Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	<input type="checkbox"/>

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Change log			
Version	Date	Author	Reason for change

Release approval			
Version	Date	Name & organisation	Role

